

OKSAROY IS A MAGNIFICENT BUILDING BUILT BY AMIR TEMUR

Guchchiyev Zayniddin Gulmurodovich

Karshi state university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10060168>

ANNOTATION: The article describes the architectural structures in Shahrisabz region during the Timurid period, their unique construction style, and architectural aspects. The unique construction aspects of the Oksaroy architectural monument are discussed. Historical sources are analyzed.

KEY WORDS: Timurids, architecture, mosque, Aksaroy, Kurgan, palace.

Amir Temur tried to turn his fatherland - Shahrisabz into the center of Muslim science in Turkestan, since it was a place where great scholars of Islam gathered in ancient times.

As the religious status of Shahrisabz increased during Temurbek's time, mudarrises of famous madrasas in Khorezm, scholars of Bukhara and Ferghana gathered, and all of them were given favorable opportunities to teach the young generation. That is why Sahibqiran's contemporaries called this magnificent city "Qubbatul ilm wal-adab", i.e. "Dome of Science and Culture", as described above. Shahrisabz has been worthy of this high title many times in later years[1].

In 1378, Temurbek ordered the construction of Shahrisabz fortress, fortress wall and tower gates. The city fortress is surrounded by a deep moat, and its gates are supported by a suspension bridge. With the construction of the foundation of the castle, Temurbek ordered the construction of a castle as majestic as Oksaroy (1380).

This amazing building attracted many scientists. Because the building was extremely magnificent and extraordinarily attractive. Historian Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi gives this information: "He built a fortress in the city in 781 (March 1380) It was such a city, the Gardun engineer traveled the world at such a young age and never saw such a beautiful city and beauty anywhere"[2].

Oksaroy was built in almost 24 years (1380-1404) due to the fact that it is a very complex, magnificent building in terms of architectural structure. Of course, the delay in its construction was caused by Temurbek's military campaigns against the builders in Samarkand. It is also possible that the construction of Oksaroy was stopped and resumed from time to time. So, although the main part of the construction of the monument was completed by Khorazmian masters, Iranian architects completed the construction.

In particular, the building itself is decorated with quiet patterns in national styles. Azerbaijani craftsmen also took part in the construction of

Oksaroy, which can be seen from the inscription on the palace facade. The name of Tabriz architect and painter Muhammad Yusuf is written on it. Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo, the ambassador of Spain (Castile), came to Samarkand to see Temurbek (August 29, 1404), stopped in Shahrisabz and visited Aksaroy. At that time, the construction work in Oksaroy was mostly completed, but the equipment work was not finished.

According to the ambassador, Oksaroy was a royal residence intended for Temurbek and his family. It contained Timur's ornate banqueting halls, living quarters for himself and his family, recreation rooms, now 300 steps, a huge inner courtyard surrounded by mountains, a large white marble pool, verandas and verandas for sale, fruit trees and landscaped gardens. there was a garden. , there were trees. Enthusiastic about Acharoi's decorations, Ambassador Clavijo said: "...there are so many rooms here that it is impossible to describe them at once. All the rooms are decorated with gold and jewels. The masters of Paris may be surprised to see it. Such works of theirs are highly appreciated"[3].

Another unique feature of the palace is that there is an ancient pond on the roof of the building, into which amber water flows through lead pipes 35 kilometers from Takhta Karacha pass in the Samarkand oasis of the Urgut mountains. It formed a waterfall and went down[4].

In its time, such a huge and majestic structure as Aksaroy was the only one in Turan and Iran. Oksaroy decorations are different from the patterns in Samarkand monuments[5].

So, Oksaroy is a great monument in the architecture of Central Asia, and it is an example of the peak of creativity of national architects.

References:

1. Qadimgi Kesh - Shahrisabz tarixidan lavhalar. Mas'ul muharrir A.S.Sagdullayev. - T.: "Sharq", 1998. - B.11
2. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdiy. Ko'rsatilgan asar. - B.88.
3. Amir Temur Yevropa elchilari nigohida. - T.: G'.G'ulom nomidagi NMIU, 2007. - B.111
4. Boburnoma. - B.47.
5. Ravshanov P. Oqsaroy tarixi. - T.: "Yangi asr avlodi", 2016; Amir Temur Yevropa elchilari nigohida. - T.: G'.G'ulom nomidagi NMIU, 2007. - B.111.

